

Characteristics of Hydraulic Jump

Authors : Sumit Gandhi

Abstract : The effect of an abruptly expanding channel on the main characteristics of hydraulic jump is considered experimentally. The present study was made for supercritical flow of Froude number varying between 2 to 9 and approach to expanded channel width ratios 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 and 0.8. Physical explanations of the variation of these characteristics under varying flow conditions are discussed based on the observation drawn from experimental results. The analytical equation for the sequent depth ratio in an abruptly expanding channel as given by Ranga Raju is verified well with the experimental data for all expansion ratios, and the empirical relation of Herbrand was verified with the present experimental data.

Keywords : Abruptly Expanding Channel, Hydraulic Jump, Efficiency, Sequent Depth Ratio

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014